

MATHEMATICS AND CRITICAL THINKING

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A specific field of study

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Annotation: This study discusses the ways to encourage critical thinking in mathematics classes and offers two methods on this. The first method is a different approach to problems, through which the teacher encourages students to think out of box. The second method is applying mathematical modeling, in which the teacher shows students the relationship between mathematics and real world.

Keywords: formulas, creative thinking, critical thinking, mathematics, theorems, modeling, real-world applications.

Аннотация: Эта статья посвящена продвижению критического мышления в математическом образовании и представляет два способа развития критического мышления. Первый метод – это иной подход к примерам, с помощью которого учитель побуждает учащихся к творческому мышлению. Второй метод – это реализация математического моделирования, при котором учитель показывает учащимся связь между математикой и реальной действительностью.

Ключевые слова: формула, творческое мышление, математика, моделирование, критическое мышление, теоремы.

Critical and creative thinking is undeniably important if we want our students to be ready for future social activities and a constantly changing world. Mathematics is very important for developing critical thinking. Many people underestimate the importance of mathematics and think that formulas, theorems and problems are nothing in life. In response to this, one can take the example of the simplest exercise that many people do – jogging in the morning. No one practices running just in case a wolf gets in their way. Running is good for health because it exercises the body, making it healthier and less likely to get sick. Math is the same. It is possible to not use this formula in life, but it makes the brain fit and healthy, and later in life, the same trained brain will be used in making various decisions and solving everyday problems. Teachers use methods that they themselves have seen as students. But today, it is very important that mathematics teachers learn to work on themselves, to encourage students to think critically in addition to the previous methods. Of course, it is not convenient for the teacher if the students ask a lot of questions. However, sometimes debating develops the skills of the student to express his opinion correctly, to defend why he is in favor of this solution. Moreover, asking the right questions is not an innate ability, it needs to be developed. In this article, we will focus on two simple ways to develop critical thinking in mathematics. A different approach to examples considering mathematics as a tool for developing critical thinking, it is necessary to understand that the purpose of mathematics lessons is not to solve examples, but to find solutions to problems by solving examples. Simply put, we need to be

able to explain mathematics in a meaningful, real-life way, not as isolated topics. Having students work in small groups to solve problems can build different skills than traditional math teaching methods. Instead of simply solving a problem, students debate among themselves, discuss different ways to approach a solution, and learn to prove and defend their solutions. Of course, this requires students to have basic background knowledge (certain formulas or theorems). In this case, the teacher should pay attention to the correct choice of the issue. The problem should be unusual and appropriate to the course and knowledge of the students. It is not appropriate to give a problem, the solution of which is obvious to everyone. It is even better if the matter can be interpreted differently. On the other hand, confusing a student who has never seen such a problem by giving it an extremely difficult problem is also not true. After all the groups have solved the problem, the teacher asks the following important questions:

- What did you think about the issue?
- Show how you went about solving the problem and why it is the right way.
- Which answer did you stop at?
- Does anyone have a different solution to the problem? (If everyone has the same method, the teacher can introduce a different method).

The main part of the whole exercise is the teacher asking the students for explanations for their solution. The teacher should explain that it is more important for the student to be able to prove his answer and show its correctness than the answer itself. In other words, if the student can't demonstrate that his solution is correct, it doesn't matter whether his answer is right or wrong, because there is no proof.

Interest in mathematical modeling

Mathematical modeling is very widely used in the professional world. Investors model market forces, entrepreneurs model inputs and outputs, environmentalists model population growth, climate change, and so on. However, due to its widespread application and its enormous potential for developing critical thinking, mathematical modeling is one of the methods that is relatively rarely used in mathematics classes.

Modeling training allows students to:

- Develops the ability to understand suffering by asking questions and making assumptions;
- Teaches to use mathematical tools in problem solving;
- Allows you to make your own decisions about how to approach the solution;
- Requires an explanation of why their method makes sense;
- Teaches to check and revise his solution.

If you think about it, everything in life can be put into a mathematical model. For example, when entering a door, if we know that someone is coming behind us, should we hold the door open for that person or not? If the person is coming at a little distance from us, our waiting with the door open will hurry the person, and he will have to run – the good we want to do becomes an inconvenience. On the other hand, closing the door when approaching is considered a sign of disrespect. So, there is an optimal distance between the two sides to keep the door open. Another example: what should a student bring from home for lunch? In this case, the student can think about what is more important to him and mathematicalize the problem (lunch=sandwich drink dessert). It takes into account factors such as the size of the lunch box, the ability to heat the lunch, and products that do not go bad. The modeling exercise helps students to take a fresh look at common techniques and learn how mathematics

can help them understand everyday situations. It is also possible to generalize such examples and give students larger projects based on their interests. Based on the above, students' levels of critical thinking in mathematics are reflected in:

- Ability to identify problems;
- Ability to find errors;
- Ability to analyze a given issue;
- Being able to apply learned concepts to new issues;
- Being able to draw conclusions from the problem.

In conclusion, the use of mathematics as a tool for critical thinking is very important at the current stage of development of our country. In today's age of new, right or wrong information, full of advertising, uncertainty and doubt and distractions, our youth need to be able to think critically. Formation is more relevant than ever.

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